

RAINBOW IN CAPTIVITY: A NARRATIVE OF PERSON DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY

Jeric C. Flores, Mariz P. Balquin

Department of Criminal Justice Education, University of Southern Mindanao, Kabacan, Cotabato, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15125166>

ABSTRACT

The primary goal of this study were to provide information about lived experiences, coping mechanisms and insights of LGBTQ inmates. The study employed a qualitative research design using phenomenological approach that seeks to understand the lived experiences LGBT PDLs. Results show that the lived experiences of the participants were expressed with two themes which were (positive experienced and negative experienced). In addition, the participants coping mechanisms were programs (spiritual, educational and livelihood); activities (recreation/sport, Zumba, and pageant); self-motivation (positive mindset and hope); and support system (jail officers and family). Moreover, the result also revealed that the insights of LGBT inmates focused on changing behavior (learnings, respect and forgiveness) and expressing gender identity (freedom on self-expression).

Keywords: *LGBT PDLs, lived experiences, coping mechanisms, insights*

INTRODUCTION

Individuals who identify as LGBTQ+ in jail frequently face many challenges. LGBTQ+ inmates face institutional bias and systematic discrimination when they are incarcerated, along with a lack of awareness and respect for their support, care, and treatment needs (Brown, 2021). According to a National LGBTQ+ Prisoner Survey conducted in 2015 found that almost 58% of LGBTQ people incarcerated reported higher levels of

depression, suicidality, interpersonal trauma, substance use disorders, and general distress as a result of prejudice, discrimination, and unfair treatment. Institutional stigma, which is fed by widespread attitudes, opinions, and preconceptions regarding the mentioned demographic, is one of the worrying causes. According to studies, for instance, the victimization, alienation, and prejudice LGBTQ+ individuals may suffer in society at large are frequently replicated and exacerbated in the prison environment (Brown, 2021).

This study was therefore focused on the LGBT PDLs specifically their lived experiences, coping mechanisms and insights inside the prison setting. Moreover, this study is very much beneficial to other LGBT members, community and government because it will provide them important information about the lived experiences of LGBT inmates. This study is important also to the jail officers and other prison official personnel which serves as their basis to develop and implement different programs and activities to protect the rights of every LGBT inmate as well as enhance their potentials and skills in the different fields. Lastly, this study is also beneficial to the future researchers because this will fill in as their aide in making future researches.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the lived experiences, coping mechanisms and insights of LGBTQ inmates. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the lived experiences of the LGBTQs being people deprived of liberty?
2. What are the coping mechanisms used by the LGBTQ?
3. What are their insights from their experiences?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used qualitative study. Qualitative is the open-ended question on the suggestion of the respondents to determine lived experiences, coping strategies and insights of rainbow captivity a person deprived of liberty. The researcher's goal is to learn about, investigate and interpret rainbow in captivity who is a person deprived of liberty. This topic ignited the researcher's interest on their lived experiences and the difficulties encountered. The researcher transcribed and coded the data for analysis. The researcher carefully analyzed and interpreted the responses after the required data had been given meaning. The participants are the source of all information used in the study. Thus, the views and perception of the researcher are not included in the data- processing to justify fairly and not to bias the study's findings. Research Participants were Six (6) selected LGBTQ+ prisoners are part in this study. One (1) from North Cotabato Provincial Jail, two (2) from Kidapawan City District Jail and three (3) from Kabacan District Jail. To acquire further data, in-depth interviews are done with the chosen respondents. Data Collection The purpose of this qualitative research study is to answer the research questions. Participants is approached and asked if they would want to participate in a study. In-depth face-to-face interviews is done. Before the interview, the researcher assured to discussed along with the interview is keep strictly confidential. Data Analysis This study utilized the

following data tools in analyzing the gathered data to determine the lived experiences of LGBTQ+ prisoner inside the jail. This was used to look for significant patterns in dataset that could help answer the research questions. The study, “Rainbow in Captivity: a Person Deprived of Liberty” was investigated using thematic analysis, which includes transcribing, coding, assigning meaning to terms, analyzing and showing the developing themes and subthemes. Validity Before administering the interview, the interview guide undergo validation by designated experts. After the validation, the interviews and data collection was done. Expert feedback and ideas were considered to improve the tools. In terms of the results’ validity, emergent themes and interpretations were confirmed by respondents and an independent researcher transcribed it to guarantee the correct interpretation and meaning.

RESULTS

1. Lived Experiences of LGBT Persons Deprived of Liberty Inside the Prison Setting

This section presents the discussion about the lived experiences of LGBT person deprived of liberty inside prison settings which includes good/positive experiences and bad/negative experiences.

2. Good/Positive Experiences

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the good/positive experiences of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis shows that the generated themes for this topic are (1) equal treatment from jail officers and (2) accessibility.

Table 1. Good/Positive Experiences

Sub-Themes	Description
Equal treatment from Jail officers	The fair and unbiased treatment of LGBTQ inmates by jail officers, ensuring they receive the same respect and rights as other inmates.
Accessibility	Ensuring that LGBTQ inmates have equal access to facilities, resources, and support services within the prison environment.

Equal treatment from Jail Officer. The Respondents stated that they receive equal treatment through respect for their identity and enjoy the same privileges as other inmates from jail officers. This theme is very important during the rehabilitation and in creating a safer and more positive environment for all inmates. This was mentioned in the responses of the respondents. According to one of the respondents:

“Nirespeto bilang bilang kalahating babae kalahating lalaki dito nila ako dito binigyan ng halaga binibigyan nila kaming pansin ng jail officer na kapwa nila lalaki at kapwa nila babae.”

I am respected and valued as someone who is not purely male or female, and the jail officers give us attention. - Respondent 3

The Respondent 3 expressed that they feel respected and valued by the jail officers who acknowledge their identity beyond traditional gender categories. According to the Fenway Institute (2019), prison staff that treat LGBTQ+ convicts with respect and equality significantly improve their psychological condition and general state of mind. This highlights the importance of using efficient procedures when handling LGBTI people in penal institutions in order to foster an environment that is welcoming. Similarly, the Williams Institute (2021) highlighted that those who identify as LGBTQ+ assert that they feel healthier and more accepted when authorities personnel manage them using dignity and equity. This greatly enhances their overall health and increases their beliefs in the judiciary. In establishing an empowering setting, the research underscores the worth of accepting behavior. Additionally, Brown and Jenness (2020) also highlighted the importance of ensuring equitable treatment for improving general security and mental health, highlighting that applying broad guidelines and procedures that guarantee the privileges and worth of LGBTQ+ prisoners may significantly decrease accountability for human rights offenses and advance fairness inside the institution of jails.

Accessibility. The Respondents stated that their needs as members of the LGBTQ community were always supported through the efforts of the jail officers, especially the Unit Welfare and Development team. According to the Respondents,

“Syempre sa... tulong ng... mga... jail officers namin especially our unit welfare and development gina... assure nila always na uhhh ma support yung aming mga pangangailangan as ahh members of the LGBTQ.”

Our jail officers, especially the unit for welfare and development, always support our needs as LGBTQ members. - Respondent 1

The Respondent 1 mentioned that the jail officers, particularly those in the unit for welfare and development, consistently support the needs of LGBTQ members. According to Trimble (2019), which at first stated the essential role of such resources in developing a supportive atmosphere, giving LGBTQ+ imprisoned the opportunity to receive educational, therapeutic, and mental wellness programs significantly improves their general health and chances of being successfully reintegrated towards the community.

Similarly, Donohue et al. (2021) revealed that ensuring those programs are available to LGBTQ+ offenders positively impacts their chances for recovery and wellness, stressing the importance of attention regarding their specific state of mind needed for the purpose of ensuring they receive suitable treatment and assistance. Furthermore, the Sentencing Project (2022) showed that LGBTQ+ offenders gain from fairly accessible corrections services by means of strengthened emotional wellness, less recidivism and improved overall security. With the aim to aid in the recovery and successful reintegration of LGBTQ+ prisoners, this research promotes comprehensive measures and efforts.

3. Bad/Negative Experiences

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the bad/negative experiences of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis show that the generated themes are (1) discrimination, (2) loneliness, (3) confused and (4) rejection from family and friends

Table 2. Bad/Negative Experiences

Sub-Themes	Description
Discrimination	Unjust or prejudicial treatment of LGBTQ inmates based on their sexual orientation or gender identity within the prison system.
Loneliness	The feeling of isolation and lack of social support experienced by LGBTQ inmates due to limited acceptance and connection within the prison environment.
Confused.	The state of being uncertain and stressed about one's identity and how to navigate the prison environment, often heightened for LGBTQ inmates.
Rejection from family and friends	The experience of LGBTQ inmates facing abandonment and disapproval from loved ones.

Discrimination. The Respondents described that facing discrimination is based on their sexual orientation or gender identity from fellow inmates within the prison. According to the Respondents,

“Minsan po na naranasan po natin yong pagbubuli o kinukutya ng mga sa kapwa natin inmate kasi wala daw akong kwenta dito sa mundo kasi lalaki babae lang daw ang dapat mabuhay hindi nila minsan matanggap na ganito tayo isa tayong LGBTQ.”

Sometimes, we experience bullying from fellow inmates who don't accept us as LGBTQ.
- Respondent 3

The Respondent 3 mentioned that they sometimes face bullying from fellow inmates who do not accept their LGBTQ identities. According to Stammen and Ghandnoosh (2022), the adverse interactions of LGBTQ+ prisoners in penal settings are made worse by the interpersonal, sexual activity, and oral bullying that they encounter, as well as their absence of gender-affirming quarters, clothing, sanitation items, and healthcare services. Similarly, Trimble (2019) highlighted the fact that LGBTQ+ prisoners experience systematic prejudices, involving serious harassment and insufficient attention in healthcare and therapeutic settings, considerably harming their internal wellness and general well-being. This persistent intolerance not only contributes to the feelings and mental disorders of LGBTQ+ convicts but also impacts their abilities to get vital support and medical care. To guarantee equal privilege and enhance the general standard of living for LGBTQ+ people in the criminal justice system, structural changes are absolutely necessary, as evidenced by the continuous abandonment and assault in these crucial areas. Furthermore, Brown and Jenness (2020) highlighted the different methods the jail officers oversee LGBT people convict, which involve short-term and long-term confinement, and talked about different types of assault that LGBT offenders receive from their fellow inmates and government personnel. They acknowledged that these acts of violence constitute human rights offenses.

Loneliness. The Respondents shared their experiences of feeling lonely due to lack of understanding from others, including their friends, about their gender identity. According to the Respondents,

“Minsan malungkot ako ahh... at masakit yong loob ko kasi hindi nila ako maintindihan kahit yong mga kaibigan ko ayaw na kasi na yata ayaw nila na tanggapin na bilang kalahating lalaki kalahating babae na ako.”

I feel sad and hurt because my friends don't accept or understand me as not purely a man. - Respondent 3

Respondent 3 expressed feeling sad and hurt because their friends do not accept or understand their non-binary identity. According to Srivastava et al. (2022), thorough unfairness and inadequate provision of treatment programs usually lead LGBTQ+ offenders to feel less supported, leading to an undesirable impact on their cognitive state and overall welfare. Since serious mental health conditions like anxiety and depressive symptoms can result from this common feeling of rejection and loneliness, it has become essential to eradicate various structural barriers. For LGBTQ+ offenders, the creation of complete and accessible treatment programs inside the justice system could seriously improve mental recovery and overall enjoyment of daily life, developing an enhanced sensitive and healing setting. Also, improving the quality of life of LGBTQ+ prisoners can be easily achieved by promoting consciousness and introducing educational activities regarding the specific challenges they encounter. Likewise, Donohue et al. (2021) observed that an absence of awareness and concern for the care, treatment, and support

needs of LGBTQ+ offenders regularly result in severe isolation, increasing their adverse situations in bars. Those in this situation become more isolated within the criminal justice system, caused by a shortage of assistance and services designed especially to address specific problems, which increases their feeling of loneliness. Applying concentrated attention and embracing attitudes is necessary for improving the way they feel and creating an enhanced fair setting since broad mistreatment and disrespect may contribute to psychological concerns. Additionally, Brown and Jenness (2020) stressed the feeling of isolation encountered by LGBTQ+ offenders caused by numerous assaults by their fellow inmates, particularly maltreatment and separation, that greatly impacts their psychological wellness and overall wellness. This extensive isolation may increase the mental consequences of imprisonment by causing intense anxiety and sadness. LGBTQ+ convicts discover hard to believe secure or respected in this setting since they are not allowed to express about their worries of assault. It is important to deal with such problems in order to build a more compassionate and hospitable prison institution that promotes the mental health and all of humanity.

Confused. The Respondents shared their experiences of feeling confused about their gender identity, questioning why they are the way they are. According to the Respondents,

“Malaking question sa akin na nangyari sa buhay minsan hindi ko hindi maisip bakit kung nagkaganito ako bakit ahh bakit ako naging kalahating lalaki kalahating babae.”

I often wonder why my life turned out this way, being half man and half woman. - Respondent 3

The Respondent 3 often wonders why their life has unfolded with a dual identity of being both man and woman. According to Brown and Jenness (2020) discuss the gender confusion faced by LGBTQ+ inmates, as well as the many abuses they face from the jail, including maltreatment and loneliness, that have a negative impact on their neurological health. Confusion and abuse intensify emotions of sensitivity and helplessness, making it challenging for many convicts to deal with their confinement. Furthermore, the absence of affection and sympathy inside the correctional facility system confines LGBTQ+ prisoners, emphasizing the pressing need for broad guidelines and practices that deal with their particular issues while also promoting their psychological and social well-being. Similarly, Donohue et al. (2021) found that LGBTQ+ inmates commonly feel severe gender confusion as a result of an absence of consciousness and concern regarding their care, treatment, and support necessities, exacerbating their bad experiences in penal settings. This uncertainty and indifference not just worsen their mental anguish, but also causes emotions of loneliness and powerlessness. The lack of appropriate assistance and specialized treatments further stigmatizes LGBTQ+ prisoners, emphasizing the necessity for equitable laws and procedures that deal with their specific difficulties and advocate their mental health. Moreover, Trimble (2019) showed how deliberate prejudice and a lack of assistance services cause profound gender confusion within jailed LGBTQ+ people, especially transgender prisoners, which has significant adverse effects on their psychological wellness and overall quality of life. Since they're incapable of

communicating their gender identities inside of the institution of corrections, transgender inmates are experiencing more emotions of sadness and isolation caused by the absence of special attention. Moreover, prevalent prejudice and poor treatment produce an unpleasant environment that reduces the aims of restoration and recovery, emphasizing how important it is for complete broad reform programs.

Rejection from family and friends. The Respondents expressed feelings of rejection and longing for their families and friends, who have not visited them for over a year. According to the Respondents,

“Mamiss ko yong pamilya ko at tsaka kaibigan ko sa labas mag sobra one-year na po akong hindi dinadalaw ayaw na siguro sa akin.”

I miss my family and friends. They haven't visited me in over a year, and I think they don't want to see me anymore. - Respondent 6

The Respondent 6 expressed feelings of deep sadness and isolation due to the absence of visits from their family and friends, leaving them to question if their loved ones still wish to see them. According to Palmer and Francis (2023), they discovered that among youths who identified as sexual minorities, there has been an important connection involving elevated feelings of depression and anxiety and parental rejection of gender identity and expression. Furthermore, this form of alienation makes LGBTQ+ offenders' psychological conditions exacerbated when they have been inside the jail. This mankind's emotional distress can be worsened with a general lack of encouragement and acceptance from their loved ones, which may result in embedded emotion of loneliness and uselessness. Similarly, the Queen's University Belfast (2022) noted that family rejection has played a major part in the psychological health problems and generally bad experiences of LGBTQ+ offenders, highlighting the importance of managing this problem to improve the prisoners' wellness. The psychological effects caused by such rejections may worsen existing difficult circumstances of imprisonment by having anxiety, sadness, and feelings of alienation. The prison system could develop an additional encouraging setting that supports cognitive wellness and facilitates rehabilitation procedures for LGBTQ+ prisoners by acknowledging and lessening the effects of familial rejection. Furthermore, Morgan (2024) also highlighted that LGBTQ+ people that spent time in jail frequently suffered from abandonment from friends and family, which can have had a major adverse effect on both their psychological state and overall state of mind. To help individuals to develop fortitude and inspire helpful reintegration into society, the research study shows the vital role that supportive family interactions play.

4. Coping Mechanisms of LGBT Person Deprived of Liberty Inside the Prison Setting

This section presents the discussion about the coping mechanisms of LGBT person deprived of liberty inside the prison setting which includes the program, activities, self-motivation, and support system.

5. Programs

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the program of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis shows that the generated themes are (1) Spiritual Program, (2) Educational Program, and (3) Vocational/ Livelihood Program.

Table 3. Programs

Sub-Themes	Description
Spiritual Program	Spiritual Program Organized activities that address the spiritual needs of LGBTQ inmates, providing a safe space for personal growth and emotional support.
Educational Program	Educational Program Learning opportunities and courses provided to LGBTQ inmates to support their personal and professional development.
Vocational/ Livelihood Program	Vocational/ Livelihood Program Skills training and work opportunities provided to LGBTQ inmates to enhance their employability and support their reintegration into society.

Spiritual Program. The Respondents stated that to support their spiritual growth, a church from Kidapawan organized a religious program for them. According to the Respondents,

“May nag religious na religious ah activity na ginawa yong taga Kidapawan na isang church sa Kidapawan to ano to para ma ano kami sir bah ma mabless kami”

A church from Kidapawan organized a religious program to bless us.
– Respondent 1

Respondent 2 also stated that participating in religious services was highly effective in aiding their personal transformation.

“Sobra effective kanang mag simba ka, maminaw sa pulong sa ginoo ana sobra kaayo kay kanang makatabang gyud siya sa ano sa imohang kanang pag bago nimo.”

Attending church and listening to God's word greatly helps in personal transformation. - Respondent 2

The Respondent 2 highlighted that attending church and engaging with God's word plays a significant role in the personal transformation of PDLs, particularly those who are LGBTQ PDLs. According to Yarhouse and Deneke (2021), the fact that the connection is rooted in faith, spirituality, and LGBTQ+ moments, displaying the ways that attached personalities contribute to strategies for coping, might be helpful for LGBTQ prisoners, and implementing religious or spiritual support may give vital resilience and courage in a correctional environment. Similarly, Menhinick and Sanders (2023) also highlighted the worth of religious support in helping the LGBTQ+ community cope with challenges and problems. LGBTQ prisoners may gain from such therapies, that address family and social factors and provide full spiritual guidance as an effective way to cope for dealing with the challenges of captivity. Furthermore, Warlick et al. (2021) studied into how religious fundamentalism influenced LGBTQ+ people's mental health, showing the importance of accessible spiritual assistance programs. The results they discovered are therefore useful to LGBTQ prisoners, and the adoption of consisting spiritual programs may improve their adjustment and overall welfare in a jail setting.

Educational Program. The Respondents stated that their participation in educational programs, such as the Alternative Learning System (ALS), has been highly beneficial. According to Respondents,

“Natutunan ko rin talaga dito sa piitan ay tulad ng pag aral ko ng ALS natuto ako bumasa natuto ako sumulat natututo rin ako nag mag plus at tsaka divide ganyan po.”

I learned to read, write, and do basic math through ALS while in jail. - Respondent 6

The Respondent 6 shared that they acquired essential skills in reading, writing, and basic math through the ALS program while incarcerated. According to Azarcon (2023), programs offered by ALS have the potential for converting prisoners into useful members of society through offering prisoners essential academic skills like basic talents, skills, reading, and job preparation. Prisoners' individual development and restoration rely upon this academic potential, which helps them be empowered, prepared for reality after discharge, and accepted. Similarly, Trimble (2019) highlighted the significance of LGBTQ inclusive programs to improve the opportunities for LGBTQ people who are imprisoned. Prisons may manage inequalities by creating a supportive atmosphere that encourages the restoration and overall wellness of LGBTQ prisoners by setting appropriate accessible educational programs. Additionally, the Department of Education (2019) states that the Alternative Learning System (ALS) at New Bilibid Prison has proven especially effective in offering offenders academic advantages that help them to cope while adjusting to their conditions in jail. This program allows prisoners to establish an appreciation of objectivity and feelings of worth, each of which are important to their process of rehabilitation, in combination with offering them useful skills and expertise. Throughout, before and after their time behind bars, the ALS program aids offenders in preparing the conditions of an environmentally beneficial and productive future by supporting lifetime education.

Vocational/Livelihood Program. The Respondents stated that they are gaining useful skills through the vocational/livelihood programs available in prison, which they can apply once they are released. According to the Respondents,

“Natututo na ako sa lahat ng bagay na hindi ko natutunan sa labas like yong livelihood program. Sa livelihood program po magagamit ko to sa labas dito sa loob ng labas ng bilangguan pagkatapos kong makalaya kasi pang kabuhayan ito.”

I am learning new things, like the livelihood program, which I can use after I am released from jail. - Respondent 3

Respondent 4 also stated that they engaged in activities such as weaving mats to earn money.

“Minsan naga gawa kami ng banig tapos ito nag bibigay sa amin ng pera sa loob ginapabenta nila sa labas.”

We weave mats to earn money. – Respondent 4

The respondents indicated that they are acquiring new skills and earning money through the livelihood program by weaving mats, which will benefit them after their release from jail. According to Estillore and Aoas (2020) show the fact that the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology's (BJMP) employment programs provide an important impact on the daily routines of released prisoners. By giving trust in yourself, societal respect, job prospects, and an extra source of income, these kinds of services improve the socioeconomic standing of the offenders additionally developing skill growth, social distraction, confidence, and friendships with fellow prisoners. Similarly, the BJMP (2020) underscored the value of livelihoods and vocational training in supporting LGBTQ offenders to learn labor-related skills and developing an overwhelming sense of intention and individuality that helps coping and correctional environment adaptation. Giving prisoners those chances help them build the trust in themselves and helpful skills they need for the lifestyle once discharged, which reduces their probability of recidivism. Also, these programs promote a more welcoming and equitable jail environment, which promotes the individual growth and reintegration of LGBTQ prisoners. Furthermore, Cabudsan et al. (2020) showed that the success of programs for rehabilitation, such as livelihood and vocational training, is illustrated by their beneficial influence on LGBTQ captives, who get important abilities and trust that support their growth as individuals and coping strategies while in jail.

6. Activities

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the activities of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis shows that the generated themes are (1) Recreation Activities (Basketball), (2) Pageant, and (3) Physical Fitness Zumba.

Table 4. Activities

Sub-Themes	Description
Recreation Activities (Basketball)	Organized sports like basketball that promote physical health, social interaction, and a sense of community among LGBTQ inmates.
Pageant	An event that allows LGBTQ inmates to express their identities, showcase talents, and build self-esteem, fostering a sense of community and acceptance within the prison.
Physical Fitness Zumba	Group dance exercise sessions that promote physical health, stress relief, and social interaction for LGBTQ inmates.

Recreation Activities (Basketball). The Respondents shared that they have access to recreational activities, such as basketball, which help them stay active and healthy. According to the Respondents,

“Doon sa kabila dating facility na open siya maka laro ka ng basketball pampapawis siya at pampaganda ng katawan hehe.”

In the other facility, we played basketball to stay fit and healthy. - Respondent 1

The Respondent 1 mentioned that playing sports inside the jail helped LGBTQ PDLs stay fit and healthy. According to Baldonado et al. (2022), LGBTQ prisoners' mental and relaxing elements benefit from social engagements such as sports, which additionally help them cope and keep up their general health. Prisoners develop an awareness of friendship and community from these events, that provides an advantageous means to deal with anxiety and depression. Participation in sports together with other recreational activities may also improve one's physical condition, that naturally correlates to improved mental wellness achievements, providing a broader approach to restoration. Similarly, Donohue et al. (2021) identified that recreational activity like playing sports could provide LGBTQ+ offenders an overwhelming sense of being accepted, increase their mental wellness, and promote a safe place for self-expression, which is important to overcome the struggles of captivity. In addition to allowing physical relief for anxiety and tension, these tasks encourage cooperation and social connection, providing offenders an appreciation of community. Moreover, the organized character of relaxation activities and sports may encourage self-control and a healthy lifestyle, each of which is advantageous for mental health. Additionally, Flores Barolo and Vicente (2019) state that LGBTQ offenders who participate in sports and other social activities provide better coping strategies and greater psychological well-being, which are important during their

adjustment to a correctional facility. The beneficial release of anxiety and distress that these kinds of activities offer helps offenders to cope with the struggles of imprisonment with greater effectiveness. Also, sporting activities can develop a therapeutic connection by means of collaboration and friendship, which helps to enhance LGBTQ prisoners' psychological strength and their sense of being a part of that group or community.

Pageant. The Respondents shared that participating in programs such as macho gay and miss gay pageants brings them joy and helps reduce stress. This theme helps them express their identities and showcase their talents to their fellow inmates. According to the Respondent 6,

“Sa mga activity yon na nga pagsali ng macho gay miss gay tapos masaya rin bawas stress”

Participating in activities like Macho Gay and Miss Gay reduces stress and makes us happy. - Respondent 6

The Respondent 6 noted that participating in activities like Macho Gay and Miss Gay helps reduce stress and brings happiness. According to Roman-Tamesis (2023) shows that beauty pageants offer LGBTQ+ people an alternative event for expressing themselves, social tests, and empowerment in the economy. Social events give the LGBTQ+ people an overwhelming feeling of dignity and feeling accepted, which is important in overcoming the difficulties of captivity. Additionally, LGBTQ+ community perseverance and feelings of determination may get substantially strengthened from beauty contests. Similarly, Abboud (2023) examined the positive effects of beauty pageants on LGBTQ+ prisoners, highlighting that these events may give them positive opportunities for building relationships and expression of themselves around a prison environment, strengthening their methods of coping for overall wellness. In addition, these contests develop connection and encouragement for captives by uniting LGBTQ+ individuals. The general state of health is significantly helped through this more profound feeling of encouragement.

Physical Fitness Zumba. The Respondents stated that to alleviate feelings of sadness and stress, they participate in group dance exercise sessions that promote physical health, stress relief, and social interaction. According to the Respondents,

“Kada umaga mag exercise kami mag zumba para naman makawala ng lungkot at stress”

We do Zumba every morning to relieve sadness and stress. - Respondent 3

The Respondent 3 mentioned that doing Zumba every morning helps alleviate sadness and stress. According to Baldonado et al. (2022), engaging in aerobic exercises like Zumba and dancing should have a beneficial impact on prisoners' relaxation and mental wellness. The research underscores that these types of events support physical health and a feeling of being connected to one another within those involved, especially

LGBTQ prisoners, who frequently face other challenges in imprisonment while additionally minimizing the pressures and challenges caused by being incarcerated. Similarly, Greenspan et al. (2019), participating in aerobic activities like Zumba contributes to a lot of benefits for LGBTQ+ youths, such as more mental and physical wellness, increasing memory and thinking abilities, and strengthening emotional and social wellness. In the correctional setting, performing those activities gives LGBTQ prisoners a necessary mechanism for releasing stress and freedom to express oneself, which builds resilience and an encouraging group. Additionally, Soleiman et al. (2021) indicated that Zumba activities positively impact participants' interpersonal and bodily effects, strengthening their mental health, relationship with others, and physical condition. Prisoners who identified as LGBTQ can benefit from Zumba and other exercise programs that encourage society, enhance overall wellness, and offer a beneficial coping strategy while incarcerated.

7. Self-Motivation

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the self-motivation of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis show that the generated themes are (1) Positive Mindset, and (2) Hope.

Table 5. Self-Motivation

Sub-Themes	Description
Positive Mindset	The adoption of an optimistic outlook and resilience by LGBTQ inmates, promoting mental well-being and coping with the challenges of prison life.
Hope	The belief in a better future and the possibility of positive change, providing emotional strength and motivation for LGBTQ inmates.

Positive Mindset. The Respondents shared their approach to maintaining a positive mindset, highlighting the support of family in overcoming problems. According to the Respondents,

“Syempre kapag may problema ka nan jan sila na pamilya mo mawawala na yan. Tawanan lang ang problema ganon lang”

When you have problems, your family is there for you, and you can just laugh them off. - Respondent 5

The Respondent 5 mentioned that having family support during tough times helps alleviate problems and provides a sense of support. According to Geddam et al. (2023), establishing an advantageous pressure attitude correctly modulates the connection between methods of coping and self-confidence. Based on this, LGBTQ offenders that exhibit a high sense of self-worth are more likely to maintain a positive perspective regarding stresses and create better coping mechanisms that will help individuals deal with the difficulties of imprisonment. Similarly, Freire et al. (2020), using a few coping strategies like preparing, assistance searching, and cognitive reappraisal raises hopes for self-confidence and promotes coping achievements. Using these approaches can assist LGBTQ offenders in maintaining a positive cognitive state and greatly enhance their capability for coping with the difficulties and pressures of captivity. Additionally, Nguyen et al. (2023) showed this Transforming Stress Program was having a major helpful effect on respondents' methods of coping and stressed thinking until six months after the program was completed. Similar initiatives might be established in effect for LGBTQ offenders aimed at helping prisoners establish a strong, cheerful situation, manage their emotional well-being, and simply feel better while being incarcerated.

Hope. The Respondents shared their feelings of hope, emphasizing the positive impact of visits from pastors and family members. This theme highlights the possibility of positive change, providing emotional strength and motivation during the rehabilitation of inmates. According to the Respondents,

“Murag malipay ka nah nakaadto sila nakaadto diri ang mga kuan pastor na kuan tapos kanang sa pamilya pud nako mas gusto na nako humanon ni tanan mag bago ko para mag kauban napud mi nila”

I'm happy that pastors and my family visited me. I want to change and finish my time here so I can be with my family again. - Respondent 2

The Respondent 5 conveyed gratitude for the visits from pastors and family, which inspire them to change and complete their prison sentence to reunite with their loved ones. According to Glazzard and Thomas (2024), it's important to encourage hope and an optimistic mindset for LGBTQ detainees, as these conditions make it possible to confront the difficulties of life behind bars, keep their feeling of a reason, and gain resiliency, each of which has a significant beneficial effect on their mental health during and after their detention. Similarly, Flores-Barolo and Vicente (2019) state that LGBTQ prisoners gain significantly from growing hope and an upbeat mentality due to these qualities allowing them to cope with life in jail and confront their problems, which at first improves their psychological wellness and overall health both inside and outside of imprisonment. Additionally, Nematy et al. (2022) pointed out the worth of hope and strength over the emotional and physical well-being of LGBTQ+ refugees and asylum seekers, helping those to cope with the difficulties of jail or prison and the relocation process. They additionally recommended the same strategies could significantly help LGBTQ offenders cope with being imprisoned and return to society.

8. Support System

This section presents and discusses the generated themes for the support system of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis show that the generated themes are (1) Family Support, and (2) Jail Officers and Personnel Support.

Table 6. Support System

Sub-Themes	Description
Family Support	Emotional and practical assistance from loved ones that helps LGBTQ inmates cope with the challenges of prison life, promoting their mental and emotional well-being.
Jail Officers and Personnel Support	Assistance and understanding from jail staff that helps LGBTQ inmates feel safe, respected, and supported in the prison environment.

Family Support. The Respondents stated that emotional and practical assistance from loved ones help them cope with the challenges of prison life. According to the Respondents,

“Naga bigay pamilya ko ng pa kain sa akin minsan twice a week, minsan GCash lang kapag hindi sila maka ano dalaw hehe tapos happy naman kahit papano”

My family brings me food twice a week or sends money through GCash if they can't visit. I'm happy with that. - Respondent 2

The Respondent 2 mentioned that receiving support from their family, such as bringing food or sending money through GCash, makes them happy. According to Morgan (2024), family support, especially acceptance, is essential to developing the cognitive condition and psychological socioeconomic status of LGBTQ captives. Through emotional resilience with successful rehabilitation within the community after post-release, this kind of assistance supports persons managing the struggles of imprisonment. Similarly, Contreras Macabangon (2023) highlighted as LGBTQ offenders' psychological state and general health are substantially enhanced by support from family members, especially among parents. This help allows them the comfort and emotional fortitude that is necessary to cope with the hardships that live in the prison setting, which are essential to their mental state and coping abilities. Furthermore, Flores-Barolo and Vicente (2019) addressed the worth of family support for supporting LGBTQ incarcerated people coping with all their struggles in the correctional facility. Regarding its psychological health and general wellness during as well as after their time in custody,

this care develops resilient emotions and a powerful sense of being connected to the wider society.

Jail officers and Personnel Support. The Respondents stated that the programs and activities provided by the jail officers enable them to showcase their talents. This theme helps them feel safe, respected, and supported in the prison environment. According to the Respondents,

“Nailalabas namin yong talento po namin dito dahil sa mga programs at activities na nabibigay po ng mga jail officers sa amin dito nila ganon po”

We can showcase our talents here because of the programs and activities provided by the jail officers. - Respondent 5

The Respondent 5 mentioned that the programs and activities provided by the jail officers enable LGBTQ PDLs to showcase their talents. According to Brown and Jenness (2020), jail staff and officers' sympathy and encouragement play a vital role in assisting LGBTQ imprisoned individuals in overcoming the difficulties of life in prison. Emotional determination, a sensation of protection, and psychological health have all benefited from this type of support. Similarly, Sanchez and Cenal (2021) also stressed the importance of jail personnel' support for LGBTQ prisoners' emotional behavior and overall happiness. Their mental health relies on a more embracing and encouraging environment, which is generated by this support as they overcome with the pressures and challenges of incarceration. Additionally, Donohue et al. (2021) discovered that correctional security personnel's treatment greatly boosts LGBTQ convicts' emotional state and overall welfare. Such support is necessary for enabling people in adapting to jail life, getting mental strength plus resilience, and overcoming those several struggles of captivity.

9. Insights of LGBT Deprived of Liberty Inside the Prison Setting

This section presents the discussion about the coping mechanisms of LGBT person deprived of liberty inside the prison setting which includes behavioral changes and gender identity.

10. Change of Behavior

This section presents and discusses the generated themes for the change of behavior of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis show that the generated themes are (1) Learnings, (2) Respect, and (3) Forgiveness.

Table 7. Change of Behavior

Sub-Themes	Description
Learnings	Positive changes in behavior resulting from educational and personal growth opportunities, aiding LGBTQ inmates in adapting and improving within the prison environment.
Respect	Mutual respect between LGBTQ inmates and their fellow inmates, promoting a sense of safety, acceptance, and positive social interactions within the prison setting.
Forgiveness	The act of letting go of resentment and seeking peace, allowing LGBTQ inmates to heal and foster positive relationships.

Learnings. The Respondents stated that their behavior has significantly changed due to the learnings and experiences gained inside the jail. According to the Respondents,

“Sa akin po naman naba nabago na po yong pani amm takbo ng buhay ko kasi dil dahil dito sa loob ng kulongan natututo ako sa lahat na dapat na gawin kong tama”

Jail has changed my life because I have learned to do what is right. - Respondent 3

The Respondent 5 mentioned that their time in jail has transformed their life by teaching them to make the right choices. According to Trimble (2019), LGBTQ detainees may still encounter significant beneficial behavioral improvements despite the prejudice that they encounter in education, recovery, and mental wellness services during imprisonment. The encounters and knowledge they get in jail may result in stronger cognitive health and attitudes during and after imprisonment. It demonstrates the value of inclusive and beneficial methods in the rehabilitation process for LGBTQ inmates. Similarly, Serisier (2022) additionally discussed specific issues that LGBTQ people experience in prison, such as organized discrimination and lack of support from other prisoners. Based on the research, psychosocial needs and attitudes can be beneficially affected by individualized therapies that deal with these issues, aiding their rehabilitation while inspiring productive mental improvements. The need for tailored treatment programs developed especially for LGBTQ prisoners. Additionally, Brown and Jenness (2020) investigated politics organizing, human rights abuses, and managerial behaviors of LGBTQ inmates. They maintain that since the educational opportunities that LGBTQ prisoners get while incarcerated aid in their personal development and recovery, supportive programs and assistance for them may result in significant beneficial mental

improvements. This highlights how essential it is to have an enabling atmosphere to promote beneficial behavioral adjustments and individual growth for LGBTQ prisoners.

Respect. The Respondents stated that to foster respect and positive behavior changes, it is essential to teach self-respect and respect for others. According to the Respondents,

“Pag pasok mo dito sa loob ng kulongan ma ano bah mabag-o ang mabago mo mabago yong ugali mo, tulad ng kung respitohin at mahal in mo yong sarili mo at sila ahh mahal in ka din ng ibang tao na nasa paligid mo”

Entering jail changes your behavior. Respect and love yourself and others, and people around you will do the same. - Respondent 1

The Respondent 1 mentioned that entering jail can significantly alter an individual's behavior. When one shows respect and love towards oneself and others, it tends to be reciprocated. According, Serisier (2022) states that LGBT detainees must be provided with respect and comprehending recognizing the critical importance of this for their neurological wellness and general health and pressing for an enhanced accepting environment. Correctional facilities can strengthen the mental capacity of LGBT prisoners through the development of acceptability and empathetic thinking which helps reduce the feeling of discrimination and alienation that they frequently encounter. Also, these broad approaches help further the goal of rehabilitation by promoting a more peaceful and productive environment within the prison setting in besides treating their offenders. Similarly, Rizzo et al. (2021) note that having regard for fellow humans matters for the welfare of both inmates and the law enforcement officials. According to their studies, prison guards that respect imprisoned people with respect build an efficient and positive environment that enhances each person's conduct and emotional wellness, including LGBTQ detainees. Additionally, Flores-Barolo and Vicente (2019) investigated the struggles that convicts at Sablayan Prison and Penal Farm encountered, finding that providing that respect from both jail staff and other inmates helps ensure the setting up of a less stressful, favorable environment, which is important for the psychological rehabilitation and emotional development of LGBTQ prisoners.

Forgiveness. The Respondents stated that learning to forgive is an important part of their rehabilitation process. According to the Respondent,

“Natutunan ko dito pag nag forgive ka maano siya bah ahh magaan siya sa loob kaya yon yong ginagawa ko dito”

Forgiving others lightens my heart, so that's what I do here. - Respondent 1

The Respondent 5 mentioned that practicing forgiveness in jail lightens their heart. According to Brown and Jenness (2020) state that forgiveness among LGBTQ prisoners provides progressive behavioral adjustments and an understanding of compassion and society inside the institution of correction, both of which affect the setting and the general

health of the convicts. In addition to eliminating pressures and problems, the traditions of repentance improve the connections from incarcerated individuals, building a more supportive and inclusive group. Additionally, the enhanced feeling of dignity and community could end up in improved cooperation and communication, which will further improve the environment and make the penal facility something less penalizing and increasingly rehabilitative. Similarly, Donohue et al. (2021) underscored those forgiveness traditions for LGBTQ prisoners leads to remarkable changes in behavior, produces social healing, and perseverance, and a supportive setting, all of which help the prisoners' psychological state and overall condition while they are detained. The substantial effect that cognitive and emotional solutions may have on the disadvantaged inside the jail system is shown by these research findings. The prison system can strengthen its own condition of LGBTQ offenders while creating a more harmonic and connected society by encouraging an attitude of forgiveness. Additionally, Srivastava et al. (2022) discovered that imprisonment reconciliation and forgiving result in significant improvements in behavior for LGBTQ inmates, fostering a more peaceful atmosphere and a better state of mind. By easing the emotional load LGBTQ prisoners bear, these activities pave the way for their acceptance and rehabilitation. In addition, providing an environment of reconciliation and forgiveness aids minimize situations of hatred and abuse, providing an improved positive and safe workplace. In besides strengthening each prisoner's wellness, this comprehensive approach encourages a more respectful and restorative criminal justice system.

11. Gender Identity

This section presents and discusses the generated themes about the gender identity of LGBT PDLs inside the prison setting. The thematic analysis shows that the generated themes are freedom of self-expression.

Table 8. Gender Identity

Sub-Themes	Description
Freedom of Self-expression	The right of LGBTQ inmates to express their identities and beliefs openly, fostering authenticity and personal empowerment.

Freedom of Self-expression. The respondents stated that being in prison allowed them to better understand and accept their true selves. This theme focused on self-expression that helps inmates to embrace their identity and fosters a more accepting and supportive environment. This was stated in the responses of the Respondents,

“Sa loob ng kulongan mas nakilala ko sarili ko na ganito pala ako na ano yang ano siya bah hindi pala ako pure na lalaki at sa katagalan natanggap ko naman at naipapakita ko rin sa kanila kung ano ako”

I discovered that I am not purely male and have accepted and embraced my true self inside the jail. – Repondent 1

Respondent 5 shared that their time in jail led them to freely express and embrace their true self, accepting that they are not purely male. According to Coppola (2023), prison settings that make it possible for LGBT detainees to freely speak about their gender orientation and one's own identity have a substantial beneficial impact on their cognitive condition and overall health, given this freedom sets up an impression of encouragement and acceptance, which is needed for the detainees' psychological and emotional health. Similarly, Brown and Jenness (2020) underscored that owing to beneficial regulations and supervision tactics that support an extra declaring and demonstrating atmosphere, which allowed LGBT detainees to come out about their sexual orientation and one's own identity within prison environments, can significantly improve psychological condition and overall health. Additionally, Dalzell et al. (2023) concluded that the mental wellness and overall well-being of LGBT convicts have been substantially enhanced by the rollout of adequate laws and psychological therapies featuring gender identification. These actions foster a friendly and uplifting imprisoned feel through enabling captives to speak about their gender and sense of self.

Conclusions

LGBTQ+ inmates navigate a harsh reality marked by violence, discrimination, and gender-based harassment. These individuals, often marginalized and misunderstood, carry within them a wealth of talents and skills. Regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity, they have the right to be treated with respect and fairness. By providing them with opportunities for rehabilitation, education, and vocational training, we can help them realize their potential and contribute positively to society.

In jail the researcher witnessed first-hand the resilience and strength of LGBTQ+ inmates. Despite the oppressive environment, many of them displayed remarkable courage and determination. They shared stories of their struggles and triumphs, revealing a deep desire for acceptance and a chance to rebuild their lives. The interviews highlighted not just the pervasive issues of violence and discrimination they face daily but also their unwavering hope for a better future.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher held a negative perspective, believing that LGBTQ+ inmates were unable to avail themselves of programs and activities due to the negative treatment from jail officers and staff. However, the experiences during and after the interviews revealed a different reality. Many LGBTQ+ inmates reported positive interactions with supportive jail officers who treated them with respect and equality. These officers played a crucial role in creating a safer and more inclusive environment,

significantly improving the well-being of LGBTQ+ inmates and helping them feel valued and understood.

After conducting the interviews, it became clear that the current system, while still having areas for improvement, had elements of support for LGBTQ+ inmates. Many of them expressed longingness for educational and vocational programs that could equip them with the skills needed to reintegrate into society. They also emphasized the importance of mental health support and counseling to help them cope with the trauma they have endured.

Despite the crimes they may have committed, LGBTQ+ inmates had the capacity to change and grow. By fostering an environment of understanding and compassion, people can help them break free from the cycle of violence and discrimination. It is crucial to implement policies and programs that promote inclusivity and respect for all inmates, regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity. By doing so, we not only uphold their human rights but also pave the way for a more just and equitable society.

Recommendations

Correctional institutions need to strengthen their policies regarding the protection of the rights and welfare of all inmates, including LGBTQ+ inmates. This includes implementing comprehensive training programs for jail officers and staff focused on LGBTQ+ sensitivity, antidiscrimination policies and inclusive practices. Establishing support groups and counseling services specifically for LGBTQ+ inmates is crucial to help them cope with trauma, build resilience, and foster a sense of community. Additionally, creating inclusive educational and vocational programs will ensure that all inmates, regardless of their sexual orientation or gender identity, have equal access to opportunities for personal and professional growth.

Promote a zero-tolerance policy for discrimination and harassment within the jail is essential. This involves enforcing strict policies, establishing clear reporting mechanisms, and ensuring that complaints are taken seriously and addressed promptly. Fostering a culture of respect and understanding among inmates and staff can be achieved through regular workshops, awareness campaigns, and open dialogues about diversity and inclusion. Collaboration with external LGBTQ+ advocacy organizations can provide valuable resources, training, and support to both inmates and jail staff, helping to develop and implement best practices for the treatment and support of LGBTQ+ inmates.

Regular assessment of the effectiveness of implemented policies and programs is necessary to ensure continuous improvement. Gathering feedback from LGBTQ+ inmates and making necessary adjustments will help identify areas for improvement and ensure that their needs are being met. Providing legal support and advocacy to LGBTQ+

inmates can help them navigate the legal system and address any injustices they may face, protecting their rights and ensuring fair treatment.

Encouraging LGBTQ+ inmates to remain patient and focused on their goals is also important. Advising them to use any negative treatment, they may encounter as inspiration to persevere and achieve their objectives can help them maintain a positive outlook and stay committed to their personal growth. By implementing these recommendations, people can create a more supportive, inclusive, and orderly prison environment that protects the rights and ensures the safety and well-being of all inmates.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to acknowledge, appreciate and owe heartfelt gratitude to everyone who helped, supported and provided assistance and guidance in the study's preparation and successful completion.

First and foremost, the researcher gives the highest honour and praises to the Almighty God for the constant guidance and strength led to the success of this study;

To his adviser Mariz P. Balquin, PhD, for all her unending guidance, support and patience in checking his drafts; and

To Ma'am Marlyn A. Resurreccion, PhD, the College of Arts and Social Sciences Dean, for the approval of this study.

The researcher would also like to express her million thanks to his ever-supportive and loving family, for their unending support and love;

To his special someone Donna Lyn T. Cleto, for being a support system and one call away girlfriend during the preparation and conduct of this study.

To everyone, his deepest gratitude for being his inspiration to accomplished this study and all those he forgot to mention, the researcher is truly thankful. May the Lord richly bless you.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher sent a written consent form to the dean of the College of Arts and Social Sciences for conducting the study. The researcher sent a written consent form to the participants and discussed it with them the benefits and conditions of their participation. The participants voluntarily joined the study. They were told that they may express their withdrawal anytime and discontinue the interview or request that their interview data be disregarded at any time. The researcher secures the data for privacy purposes. All participants were treated fairly and were not discriminated. The voice record and verbal interview shall not be uploaded to any online platforms and not to be reused. The participants were assigned a code name. The list connecting their name to the code name and the informed consent were kept. When the study was completed and the data were analyzed, the list and the recorded files were destroyed. The researcher would also ask

the participants for permission to record the session during the interview. The recording was used to transcribe the results.

REFERENCES

- Abboud, M. (2023). "Beauty Pageants: Degrading or Empowering?" SSRN. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4311201>
- Azarcon, R. O. (2023). "Education behind bars: An analysis of the Alternative Learning System program of the Bulacan State University Extension Services Office." Bulacan State University. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED596774.pdf>
- Baldonado, N. N., Demot, A. M. L., Villaflora, P. J. A., Dayag, G. G., Buado, E. L., Ramos, C. V., Dela Cruz, G. V. T., & Martinez, R. G. (2022). "Physical Activity Participation of Persons Deprived of Liberty in Santiago City District Jail, Philippines." *Physical Education and Sport: Studies and Research*, 1(2), 91-106. Retrieved from <https://jse.rezkimedia.org/index.php/pes/article/download/114/29>
- Brown, J. A., & Jenness, V. (2021). LGBT people in prison: Management strategies, human rights violations, and political mobilization. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Criminology and Criminal Justice*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264079.013.647>
- Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP). (2020). "Bureau of Jail Management and Penology Livelihood Program in Valenzuela City Jail." *Ascendens Asia Singapore – Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1), 1-10. Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcjpmra/article/view/1436>
- Cabudsan, R., Turreda, M. L., Ronilo, G., Martinez, J., Soria, M. A., & Osorio, D. A. (2020). "Effectiveness of Rehabilitation Program in Valenzuela City Jail." *Ascendens Asia Singapore – Bestlink College of the Philippines Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1), 1-10. Retrieved from <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/aasgbcjpmra/article/view/1442>
- Contreras Macabangon, E. (2023). "Out Of The Closet: Parental Response And Coping Behaviors Of Filipino Parents With Openly Self-Identified LGBTQIA+ Youth." *College of Human Ecology, University of the Philippines Los Baños*. Retrieved from <https://che.uplb.edu.ph/thesesdata/out-of-the-closet-parental-response-and-coping-behaviors-offilipino-parents-with-openly-self-identified-lgbtqia-youth/>
- Coppola, F. (2023). Gender identity in the era of mass incarceration: The cruel and unusual segregation of trans people in the United States. *International Journal of Constitutional Law*, 21(2), 649-672. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icon/moad0461>.
- Cornelius, G. (2022). *Transgender Inmates: Treating Them Fairly, Keeping Them Safe*. https://www.lexipol.com/resources/blog/addressing-housing-and-safety-for-transgender-inmates/?fbclid=IwAR2M3_E-CEHiLqkPwNIj9Ao_X2JCHInHncRTKL2wMrv-KXdSWC7S5qOUwOI
- Dalzell, L. G., Pang, S. C., & Brömdal, A. (2023). "Gender affirmation and mental health in prison: A critical review of current corrections policy for trans people in Australia and New Zealand." *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 58(1), 21-36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00048674231195285>
- Department of Education. (2019). "New Bilibid Prison's persons deprived of liberty earn basic education diploma through ALS." Department of Education. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/07/24/newbilibid-prisons-persons-deprived-of-liberty-earn-basic-educationdiploma-through-als/>
- Donohue, G., McCann, E., & Brown, M. (2021). Views and experiences of LGBTQ+ people in prison regarding their psychosocial needs: A systematic review of the qualitative research

- evidence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(17), 9335. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18179335>
- Estillore, D. B., & Aoas, D. M. P. (2020). "Effects of BJMP Livelihood Program to the Lives of Released Inmates." *International Journal of Innovative Research and Studies*, 2(11), 1-10. Retrieved from <https://ijisrt.com/assets/upload/files/IJISRT20NOV459.pdf>
- Fenway Institute. (2019). Emerging best practices in the management of LGBTI people in correctional settings. Retrieved from <https://fenwayhealth.org/report-identifies-emerging-best-practices-in-the-management-of-lgbti-people-in-correctional-settings/>
- Fernandes, F. L., Kaufmann, B., & Kaufmann, K. (2021). *LGBT+ people in prisons: Experiences in England and Scotland*. University of Dundee. <https://discovery.dundee.ac.uk/en/publications/lgbt-people-in-prisonsexperiences-in-england-and-scotland-full-r>
- Flores-Barolo, M. G., & Vicente, J. B. (2019). "Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of Persons Deprived of Liberty of Sablayan Prison and Penal Farm in the Philippines." *International Journal of Advanced Research and Studies*, 4(11), 1-10. Retrieved from <https://garph.co.uk/IJARMSS/Nov2019/G-2759.pdf>
- Freire, C., Ferradás, M. M., Regueiro, B., Rodríguez, S., Valle, A., & Núñez, J. C. (2020). "Coping Strategies and Self-Efficacy in University Students: A Person-Centered Approach." *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 841. Retrieved from <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychology/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00841/full>
- Garcia, L. (2022). *The Incarceration of LGBTQ+ People: A Portrayal of Queer Individuals in Prison Through Popular Media*. California State University San Marcos. <https://scholarworks.calstate.edu/downloads/4q77fx95n>
- Geddam, S., Jeyavel, S., Eapen, J. C., & Deepthi, D. P. (2023). "Stress mindset as a mediator between self-efficacy and coping styles." *Health Psychology Research*, 1(1), 1-15. Retrieved from <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/23311908.2023.2255048>
- Glazzard, J., & Thomas, S. (2024). "In Conversation: LGBT+ Transitions Before and During Prison." *International Journal of Educational and Life Transitions*, 3(1), 7. Retrieved from <https://ijelt.dundee.ac.uk/articles/10.5334/ijelt.85>
- Greenspan, S. B., Griffith, C., & Watson, R. J. (2019). "LGBTQ+ Youth's Experiences and Engagement in Physical Activity: A Comprehensive Content Analysis." *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 16(3), 1-15. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40894-019-00110-4>
- Griffith, D. (2019). LGBTQ youth are at greater risk of homelessness and incarceration. https://www.prisonpolicy.org/blog/2019/01/22/lgbtq_youth/
- Menhinick, K. A., & Sanders, C. J. (2023). LGBTQ+ Stress, Trauma, Time, and Care. *Pastoral Psychology*, 72(3), 367-384. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11089-023-01073-z>.
- Morgan, S. (2024). "Family Reaction as a Developmental Turning Point Among Formerly Incarcerated LGBTQ+ Adults." *Journal of Developmental and Life-Course Criminology*. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40865-024-00258-1>
- Nematy, A., Namer, Y., & Razum, O. (2022). "LGBTQI+ Refugees' and Asylum Seekers' Mental Health: A Qualitative Systematic Review." *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 20(3), 636-663. Retrieved from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13178-022-00705-y>
- Nguyen, T., Pu, C., Waits, A., Tran, T. D., Ngo, T. H., Huynh, Q. T. V., & Huang, S.-L. (2023). "Transforming stress program on medical students' stress mindset and coping strategies:

- a quasi-experimental study." *BMC Medical Education*, 23(1), 587. Retrieved from <https://bmcmmededuc.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12909-02304559-9>
- Palmer, C. W., & Francis, S. E. (2023). The role of family rejection of gender expression on minority stress and mental health of sexual and gender minority adolescents. *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 21(6), 998-1013. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13178-023-00881-5>
- Peck, S. (2022). The criminal justice system and the LGBTQ community: An anti-queer regime. *Research Journal of Justice Studies and Forensic Science*, 10(1), Article 5. <https://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/themis/vol10/iss1/5/>
- Pendharkar, E. (2022). Incarcerated LGBTQ Youth Are Struggling. Here's How Bad It Is. <https://www.edweek.org/leadership/incarcerated-lgbtq-youthare-struggling-heres-how-bad-it-is/2022/12>
- Queen's University Belfast. (2022). Out on the inside: The rights, experiences and needs of LGBT people in prison. Retrieved from <https://pure.qub.ac.uk/en/publications/out-on-the-inside-the-rights-experiences-and-needs-of-lgbt-people>
- Radice, A. (2020). An Exploration of the Lived Experience of Transgender Individuals in Prison. *Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies*. <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=10703&context=dissertations>
- Rizzo, D., Davey, B., & Irons, M. (2021). Interpersonal Interaction Between Prisoners and Officers in Prisons: A Qualitative Meta-Synthesis Exploring Prison Officer Wellbeing. *Qualitative Criminology*, 10(1). Retrieved from <https://www.qualitativecriminology.com/pub/v10i1p4/release/1>
- Roman-Tamesis, J. (2023). "Beyond the Crown: Exploring Queer Narratives and Transformation in Philippine Beauty Pageants." *PCS Review Series*, 89-128. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Janice-Roman-Tamesis/publication/377019809_Beyond_the_Crown_Exploring_Queer_Narratives_and_Transformation_in_Philippine_Beauty_Pageants/links/6592803d6f6e450f19ba5a7c/Beyond-the-Crown-Exploring-QueerNarratives-and-Transformation-in-Philippine-Beauty-Pageants.pdf
- Sanchez, F. F., & Cenal, K. (2021). "Towards a Gender-Responsive Jail and Prison Development: A Dialogue with the BJMP and BUCOR." *JJCICSI*. Retrieved from <https://jjcicsi.org.ph/towards-a-gender-responsive-jailand-prison-development-a-dialogue-with-the-bjmpl-and-bucor/>
- Sentencing Project. (2022). Incarcerated LGBTQ+ adults and youth. Retrieved from <https://www.sentencingproject.org/app/uploads/2022/10/Incarcerated-LGBTQ-Youth-and-Adults.pdf>.
- Serisier, T. (2022). *LGBTQ People in Prison*. Oxford Bibliographies. Retrieved from <https://www.oxfordbibliographies.com/display/document/obo-9780195396607/obo-9780195396607-0318.xml>
- Soleiman, M., Elkilany, A. M., Al-Sayed, H., & Abdelsalam, R. (2021). "The Effectiveness of Zumba Exercises Training on the Physical and Health Course Outputs among University Students." *International Journal of Human Movement and Sports Sciences*, 9(2), 316-323. Retrieved from <https://www.hrpub.org/download/20210330/SAJ20-19922518.pdf>
- Srivastava, A., Prost, S. G., & Williams, S. M. (2022). Mental health among lesbian, gay, bisexual and other non-heterosexual adults in United States prisons. *Current Psychology*, 42, 27709–27718. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03777-6>
- Stammen, E. (2022). Incarcerated LGBTQ+ adults and youth. *The Sentencing Project Research and Advocacy for Reforms*.

- <https://www.sentencingproject.org/app/uploads/2022/10/IncarceratedLGBTQ-Youth-and-Adults.pdf>
- Stammen, E., & Ghandnoosh, N. (2022). Incarcerated LGBTQ+ adults and youth. The Sentencing Project. Retrieved from <https://www.sentencingproject.org/app/uploads/2022/10/IncarceratedLGBTQ-Youth-and-Adults.pdf>
- Trimble, P. E. (2019). Ignored LGBTQ prisoners: Discrimination, rehabilitation, and mental health services during incarceration. *LGBTQ Policy Journal*, 9, 31-38. <https://studentreview.hks.harvard.edu/ignored-lgbtq-prisonersdiscrimination-in-education-rehabilitation-and-mental-health-servicesduring-incarceration/>
- Warlick, C. A., Lawrence, R., & Armstrong, A. (2021). Examining fundamentalism and mental health in a religiously diverse LGBTQ+ sample. *Spirituality in Clinical Practice*, 8(2), 85-98. <https://doi.org/10.1037/scp0000228>
- Williams Institute. (2021). Discrimination and harassment by law enforcement officers in the LGBT community. Retrieved from <https://williamsinstitute.law.ucla.edu/publications/lgbt-discrim-lawenforcement/>
- Yarhouse, M. A., & Deneke, E. (2021). Introduction to special issue on clinical developments at the intersection of religious, spiritual, and LGBTQ+ experiences. *Spirituality in Clinical Practice*, 8(2), 77-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/scp0000263>